

Reactions of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) Chlorides with Some Aliphatic Ketones

M. S. GILL, H. S. AHUJA and G. S. RAO

Chemistry Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay, Bombay 400 085

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The reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chlorides with ethylmethyl ketone (EMK) and diethyl ketone (DEK) have been investigated to study their co-ordination behaviour. When these chlorides and ketones are reacted in 1 : 1 molar ratio, tantalum(V) chloride forms simple adduct of the type $TaCl_5 \cdot L$ ($L = EMK$ or DEK), whereas in the case of niobium(V) chloride, an oxygen-abstracted product $(NbCl_4)_2O \cdot 2L$ is obtained. With excess of the ketone, in all the cases, an oxygen abstracted compound of the type $MOCl_4 \cdot 2L$ is obtained. Infrared spectral studies ($4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) indicate the co-ordination of the ketones through the oxygen atom of the carbonyl group and that the oxygen abstracted products $MOCl_4 \cdot 2L$ and $(NbCl_4)_2O \cdot 2L$ have $M-O-M$ type of bonding. The possible mechanism for oxygen abstraction is discussed.

FAIRBROTHER et al.^{1,2} observed that in the reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) halides with large excess of oxygen containing ligands such as sulphoxides, triphenylphosphine oxide and triphenylarsine oxide, abstraction of oxygen from the ligand takes place resulting in the formation of oxyhalide complexes of the type $MOX_3 \cdot 2L$. Later Brown and coworkers^{3,4} found that 1 : 1 complexes of these metal halides could be prepared if the halide and phosphine oxides were reacted in equimolar ratios. In an earlier communication⁵, we reported 1 : 1 type of complexes of these metal halides with aromatic ketones (acetophenone and benzophenone). In the present communication we wish to report our studies on the reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chlorides with aliphatic ketones, i.e., ethylmethyl ketone (EMK) and diethyl ketone (DEK). The reactions were carried out by employing equimolar amounts of the reactants and also large excess of the ligand over the chlorides.

Experimental

The pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum were prepared and purified as described earlier⁵. Ethylmethyl ketone and diethyl ketone were purified by fractional distillation from anhydrous calcium chloride. All the organic solvent were of AnalaR grade. They were further dried by appropriate drying agents and fractionally distilled. Niobium(V) oxytrichloride was prepared by the action of dry oxygen on the pure pentachloride⁶. Found Nb 42.85%, Cl 50.20%, calculated for $NbOCl_3$, Nb 43.15% Cl, 49.40%.

All operations were carried out in a dry box containing phosphorus(V) oxide which was continuously flushed with dry nitrogen or on vacuum line using standard techniques. The general

procedure for the preparation and analysis of these compounds have been described earlier^{5,7,8}. The infrared spectra ($4000-650\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the compounds were recorded as Nujol mull on Perkin-Elmer IR Spectrophotometer Model-21, using sodium chloride optics.

Gas chromatographic analysis was done using an instrument fabricated in this Division fitted with flame ionisation detector. The mobile phase employed was 'carbowax 1500' and nitrogen was used as carrier gas.

Depending on the molar ratio of the reactants used, the reactions can be divided into two categories, one, where the reactants were taken in 1 : 1 molar ratio and the other where large excess of the ligand was employed. The reactions were carried out in carbon tetrachloride and/or methylene chloride. The following systems are described as examples for each type of reaction.

Niobium(V) Chloride-Diethyl Ketone

$NbCl_5$ (3.3 g, 12.21 mM) was suspended in carbon tetrachloride. Diethyl ketone (1.05 g, 12.24 mM) dissolved in carbon tetrachloride was added slowly to this suspension and the mixture was stirred for four hours. The yellow coloured suspension immediately changed to red coloured solution which further changed to orange on standing. On further stirring dark-brown solid separated out from the solution sticking to the sides of the reaction flask. The reaction was allowed to continue overnight and the solvent and excess of the reactant were removed by decantation. The dark-brown gummy solid was washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried *in vacuo* for 5-6 hours. The analytical results given in

Table 1, showed the compound to be $(\text{NbCl}_4)_2 \cdot 0.2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{CO}$.

Tantalum(V) Chloride-Excess of Diethyl Ketone

Diethyl ketone (3.01 g; 35 mM) was added slowly to a stirred suspension of TaCl_5 (2.176 g; 6.07 mM) in carbon tetrachloride (30 ml), when the white coloured suspension changed to yellow on addition of the ketone. On further stirring, an orange coloured solid started separating out at the sides of the reaction flask. The reaction was allowed to continue for four days. The amount of orange coloured product increased during this period and the supernatant liquid changed to light orange colour. The solvent and the excess ketone were removed by decantation and the solid was washed with carbon tetrachloride and dried *in vacuo* for 6-7 hours. The analytical results (Table 1) showed the compound to be $\text{TaOCl}_3 \cdot 2(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{CO}$.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data on the reactions with DEK and EMK are summarised in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. Contrary to our earlier results with acetophenone and benzophenone⁵, niobium(V) chloride when reacted with equimolar proportions of the above two ketones did not yield the 1 : 1 adducts, but a product having metal to chloride ratio of 1 : 4 was invariably obtained. The analysis of this product closely resembled a compound of the stoichiometry $(\text{NbCl}_4)_2 \cdot 0.2\text{L}$, where $\text{L} = \text{DEK}$ or

EMK. It is, however, interesting that in the case of tantalum(V) chloride 1 : 1 adducts were isolated in both the cases. The reactivity of these halides with the aliphatic ketones show that niobium has greater affinity towards oxygen as compared to tantalum. The greater tendency of niobium towards oxygen abstraction is well known and reported by several workers earlier⁹⁻¹⁴.

In the present study the reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chlorides with excess of ketones have resulted in the abstraction of oxygen from the ketone molecule and the formation of the corresponding oxytrichloride complexes. This observation suggests the possibility of synthesis of such complexes by the direct reaction of metal oxytrichloride and the ketone. The compound $\text{NbOCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{DEK}$ was, therefore, also prepared by this route, using methylene chloride as solvent and found to be indential with the one isolated from the reaction niobium(V) chloride with excess of DEK (Table 1).

It is known that niobium(V) and tantalum(V) halides form 1 : 1 adducts with aliphatic ethers¹⁵ even if the ligands were present in large excess. However, when these adducts were heated to about 150° they decomposed with the formation of oxytrichloride. Since the process of abstraction could be temperature dependent, it is quite likely that it may be inhibited at a lower temperature. With this view, the reaction of niobium(V) chloride with excess of DEK was carried out at about 0° which also resulted in the formation of $\text{NbOCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{L}$.

TABLE 1—REACTIONS WITH DIETHYL KETONE (L_D)

Reactant	Solvent	Reactions type	Product	Colour	Found (%)				Analyses			
					Metal	Chloride	Carbon	Hydrogen	Metal	Chloride	Carbon	Hydrogen
NbCl_5	CCl_4	Equimolar	$(\text{NbCl}_4)_2 \cdot 0.2 \text{L}_D$	Dark-brown	30.9	43.54	19.48	2.92	28.26	43.13	18.25	3.04
TaCl_5	CCl_4	"	$\text{TaCl}_5 \cdot \text{L}_D$	White	42.14	39.27	12.45	3.26	40.71	39.89	13.51	2.95
NbCl_5	CCl_4	Excess ligand	$\text{NbOCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{L}_D$	Brown	23.90	27.95	—	—	24.00	27.46	—	—
TaCl_5	CCl_4	"	$\text{TaOCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{L}_D$	Orange	38.86	22.57	22.90	4.57	38.06	22.87	25.24	4.20
NbOCl_3	CH_2Cl_2	"	$\text{NbOCl}_3 \cdot 2 \text{L}_D$	Brown	24.85	27.01	29.06	4.66	24.00	27.46	30.99	5.16

* Reactions carried out at about 0°.

TABLE 2—REACTIONS WITH ETHYLMETHYL KETONE (L_E)

Reactant	Solvent	Reactions type	Product	Colour	Found (%)				Analyses			
					Metal	Chloride	Carbon	Hydrogen	Metal	Chloride	Carbon	Hydrogen
NbCl_5	CH_2Cl_2	Equimolar	$(\text{NbCl}_4)_2 \cdot 0.2\text{L}_E$	Dark-brown	31.08	44.71	14.24	2.1	29.49	45.03	15.25	2.54
TaCl_5	CCl_4	"	$\text{TaCl}_5 \cdot \text{L}_E$	White	41.90	40.30	10.90	2.76	42.04	41.18	11.15	1.86
NbCl_5	CCl_4	Excess ligand	$\text{NbOCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{L}_E$	Dark-brown	25.4	29.3	—	—	25.8	29.6	—	—
TaCl_5	CCl_4	"	$\text{TaOCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{L}_E$	Orange	40.9	22.4	19.2	3.3	40.4	23.7	21.5	3.6

The compounds isolated from various reactions described above did not have definite melting points but turned dark when heated in sealed capillaries in the range 100-150°. They were extremely sensitive to atmospheric moisture and changed their colour on slight exposure. They were highly soluble in acetonitrile and ethyl alcohol but sparingly soluble in methylene chloride and chloroform. They were almost insoluble in common non-polar solvents.

Infrared Spectra

In the case of the 1 : 1 complexes of TaCl₅, the i.r. spectra show only minor deviation except for $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ with respect to the corresponding spectra of the ligands (Table 3). The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$

1530 cm⁻¹ in the compound formed by the reaction of acetylacetonone with niobium oxytrichloride was observed by Djordjevic and Katovic¹¹ and assigned as a combination band. These workers^{11,12} have further assigned a strong band at 934 cm⁻¹ to the terminal $\nu(\text{M}=\text{O})$ and band appearing in the region 850-750 cm⁻¹ to the presence of bridging oxygen (M-O-M) in the niobium oxytrichloride complexes with 2,2'-bipyridyl and acetylacetonone. Since the bands observed in the present study lie in the latter range, (870-780 cm⁻¹ Table 3) it shows that these compounds have bridging oxygen of the type M-O-M and are polymeric in nature. Copley et al¹, have also concluded the presence of M-O-M type of bonding in the complexes MOX₃.2L (where M=Nb or Ta; X=Cl or Br and L=sulphoxides)

TABLE-3

Compound	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ cm ⁻¹	$-\Delta\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ cm ⁻¹	$+\Delta\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ cm ⁻¹	M-O-M cm ⁻¹
Diethyl ketone L _D	1717 vs	—	1178 ms	—	—
(NbCl ₄) ₂ O.2L _D	1665 vs	72	1180 ms	7	870 vs, b
TaCl ₅ .L _D	1698 s	84	1195 m	22	—
NbOCl ₃ .2L _D	1655 s	62	1190 m	17	870 vs, b, 823 s
TaOCl ₃ .2L _D	1650 vs	67	1180 w	7	862 vs, b, 830 s
Ethylmethyl ketone (L _E)	1718 vs	—	1170 m	—	—
(NbCl ₄) ₂ O.2L _E	1656 s	62	1178 m	8	870 vs, b
TaCl ₅ .L _E	1642	76	1190 m	20	—
NbOCl ₃ .2L _D	1660 vs	58	1195 m	22	865 vs, b
TaOCl ₃ .2L _D	1653 vs	65	1185 ms	15	862 vs, b 787 s

s=strong; m=medium; w=weak; v=very; b=broad.

appear at lower frequencies in the complexes as compared to the free ligands which establish the complex formation through the carbonyl group⁵. It was observed that whereas $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ moves to the lower frequencies on complexation, $\nu(\text{C}-\text{C})$ shows a positive shift, as has also been observed by Paul and Chadha¹⁶ for ketone complexes with various Lewis acids. Also, the lowering of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ is much larger in the case of aromatic ketones⁵ (135-214 cm⁻¹) as compared to the aliphatic ketones (76 and 84 cm⁻¹), which is in conformity with the fact that the aromatic ketones have more polarisable carbonyl group as compared to the aliphatic ketones¹⁷.

The carbonyl stretching frequencies in the spectra of MOCl₃.2L (M=Nb or Ta; L=EMK or DEK) obtained either as reaction products or synthesized directly have shifted by 57-67 cm⁻¹ towards the low frequency region from those observed for the free ligand. The band observed at about 1550 cm⁻¹ in all the spectra of the complexes, MOX₃.2L, in addition to the co-ordinated $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at 1650 to 1660 cm⁻¹ may be assigned as combination band arising predominantly from the sym $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ of the co-ordinated C=O group and C-H deformation band found in the ligand itself. Similar bands at about 1430 cm⁻¹ in addition to the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ at

which are also polymeric in nature. A strong and sharp absorption band at 938 cm⁻¹ in the complex NbOCl₃.2(C₆H₅)₃PO observed by Brown et al⁸ was assigned to the terminal Nb=O. Similarly $\nu(\text{M}=\text{O})$ has been observed at 967 and 951 cm⁻¹ for complexes¹³ NbOCl₃.L and NbOBr₃.L respectively (L=*o*-phenylenebisdimethylarsine).

The i.r. spectra of the compounds (NbCl₄)₂O.2L (where L=EMK or DEK) also show negative shifts in the $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ (Table 3). This, again, confirms that the bonding of the ketones to the metal is through the carbonyl group. The most important difference in the spectra of these compounds as compared to the normal 1 : 1 adducts is the appearance of a strong band at about 870 cm⁻¹ (Table 3) indicating the Nb-O-Nb type of bonding in these compounds.

Oxygen Abstraction

The abstraction of oxygen from ligands such as sulphoxides, triphenylphosphine oxide and triphenylarsine oxide, is known to occur when these ligands are reacted with molybdenum pentachloride¹⁸, silicon tetrachloride¹⁹, niobium(V) and tantalum(V) halides¹⁻⁴. The abstraction of oxygen from aliphatic ketones has also been reported in their reactions with MoOCl₂²⁰. In the present study

of the reactions of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chlorides with excess of ethylmethyl ketone or diethyl ketone resulting in the formation of the compound $\text{MOCl}_3 \cdot 2\text{L}$, the probable course of the reaction is via the formation of oxytrichloride

The metal oxytrichloride being a Lewis acid will have tendency to co-ordinate with the available ligand molecules

If the above two reactions are taking place simultaneously, then one could expect an intermediate halogenated reaction product corresponding to the ketone used. The evidence for this chlorinated by-product from these reactions was obtained by gas liquid chromatographic analysis of the filtrate. An additional peak, having a higher retention time, presumably corresponding to the chlorinated product, appeared in the g.l.c. pattern of the filtrate solution. Similar chlorinated by-products were earlier identified in the reactions of these metal halides with other oxygen-containing donors^{1,2} as sulphoxides and triphenylphosphine oxides.

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References

1. D. B. COPLEY, F. FAIRBROTHER, K. H. GRUNDY and A. THOMPSON, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1964, **6**, 407.
2. D. B. COPLEY, F. FAIRBROTHER and A. THOMPSON, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1965, **8**, 256.
3. D. BROWN, J. F. EASEY and J. G. H. DU-PRÉZ, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1966, 258.
4. D. BROWN, J. HILL and C. E. F. RICHARD, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 476.
5. M. S. GILL, H. S. AHUJA and G. S. RAO, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1970, **21**, 447.
6. F. FAIRBROTHER, A. H. COWLEY and N. SCOTT, *J. Less-Common Metals*, 1959, **1**, 206.
7. M. S. GILL, H. S. AHUJA and G. S. RAO, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1973, **7**, 359.
8. M. S. GILL, H. S. AHUJA and G. S. RAO, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.* 1974, **36**, 3781.
9. M. C. MARIGNAO, *Ann. Chem. Phys.*, 1966, **8**, 5.
10. D. C. BARADLEY, W. WARDLAW and A. WHITELAY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 1139.
11. C. DJORDJEVIĆ and V. KATOVIĆ, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1963, **25**, 1099.
12. C. DJORDJEVIĆ and V. KATOVIĆ, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 3382.
13. R. J. H. CLARK, D. L. KEPERT and R. S. NYHOLM, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 2877.
14. J. C. DEWAN, D. L. KEPERT, C. L. RASTON and A. H. WHITE, *J. C. S. Dalton*, 1975, 2031.
15. A. H. COWLEY, F. FAIRBROTHER and N. SCOTT, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3133.
16. R. C. PAUL and S. L. CHADHA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1969, **31**, 1679.
17. D. COOK, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1961, **39**, 1184.
18. S. M. HORNER and S. Y. TYREH JR., *Inorg. Chem.*, 1962, **1**, 122.
19. M. F. LAPPERT and J. K. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 3224.
20. C. G. BARRACKLOUGH and D. J. KEW, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1970, **23**, 2387.